

Real-time Attack Simulation and Detection Using WAZUH and Telegram Alerts

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A. VIRTUAL ENVIRONMENT TESTING

This test is carried out to verify that all network and Wazuh configurations are running properly before attack detection testing is carried out. At this stage, verification is carried out to ensure connectivity between network segments and the status of the Wazuh Agent.

Table 1 Virtual Environment Testing

No	Test Case	Command	Expectation
1	Access from the User Segment to the DMZ Segment	ping 172.16.32.2	The User can access the DMZ segment (ping reply received).
2	Access from the User Segment to the Server Farm and Management Segments	ping 10.10.20.3 ping 172.16.0.1	The User cannot access the SF and Management segments (ping timeout received).
3	Access from the Management Segment to the Server Farm and DMZ Segments	ping 10.10.20.3 ping 172.16.32.2	The Administrator can access the SF and DMZ segments (ping reply received).
4	Status of the Wazuh Agent	Buka Wazuh Dashboard pada bagian <i>endpoint summary</i>	Wazuh is running, and the agent installed on the web server is actively monitored in the dashboard and is sending logs.
5	Access to the Web Application	URL: <i>http://172.16.32.2/DVWA</i>	The User can access the application without any security events being triggered.

6	Access from the Wazuh Server to the Telegram API	<code>ping api.telegram.org</code>	The Wazuh server can access the Telegram API (ping reply received).
7	Access to the Web Application 100 Times	<code>python3 ./normal_request_web.py</code>	The User can access the application normally (200 response), with no security events.
8	Access to XSS-Vulnerable Web Application URLs 100 Times	<code>python3 ./normal_request_xss_url.py</code>	The application is accessible normally (200 response), with no security events.
9	Access to SQLi-Vulnerable Web Application URLs 100 Times	<code>python3 ./normal_request_sql.py</code>	The application is accessible normally (200 response), with no security events.
10	SSH Login Access to the Web Server, Database Server, and Wazuh Server	<code>ssh eve@172.16.32.2 ssh eve@10.10.20.2 ssh eve@10.10.20.3</code>	The Administrator successfully logs in to the web server, database server, and Wazuh server, and a "user login success" event is recorded.

Table 1 presents tests conducted to verify the connectivity and functionality of the virtual environment that has been built. The tests include connectivity checks, policy enforcement verification, and service validation, such as inspecting the functionality of the web server and Wazuh.

B. SYSTEM TESTING

Scenario access for system testing detection and automatic notification send are shown in Table 2 below:

Table 2 System Testing

No	Test Case	Command	Expectation
1	DDoS Attack – Slow HTTP GET with 1000 Requests	python3 ./auto_d dos_attack_get.p y	User access is disrupted because many GET requests are sent slowly. DoS-related security events were detected in SIEM Wazuh, with alert level 10 or higher notifications sent to Telegram
2	DDoS Attack – Slow HTTP POST with 1000 Requests	python3 ./auto_d dos_attack_post. py	User access is disrupted because many POST requests are sent slowly. DoS-related security events were detected in SIEM Wazuh, with alert level 10 or higher notifications sent to Telegram
3	SQL Injection Attack – Get DVWA User List	Input: ' OR '1'='1 di form input SQLi	The entered query returns a list of users from the DVWA database. Wazuh SIEM detects SQLi attack attempts and logs events as potential attacks
4	SQL Injection Attack – Get Database Version	Input: '%' or 0=0 union select null, version() # di form input SQLi	The entered query returns the database version used by DVWA. SIEM Wazuh detects SQLi attacks and generates events as potential attacks

5	SQL Injection Attack – 50 SQL Injection Payload Requests	<code>python3./auto_sqli_attack.py</code>	SIEM Wazuh mendeteksi banyaknya upaya serangan SQLi dalam waktu singkat, menghasilkan <i>event</i> keamanan terkait SQLi
6	Reflected XSS Attack – Web Cookies	Input: <code><script>alert(document.cookie)</script></code> di form input XSS	Wazuh SIEM detects a large number of SQLi attack attempts in a short period of time, generating SQLi-related security events
7	DOM XSS Attack – Web Cookies	<code>http://172.16.32.2/DVWA/vulnerabilities/xss_d/?default=<script>alert(document.cookie)</script></code>	The URL entered runs a JavaScript script that displays cookies. SIEM Wazuh records XSS events as potential attacks and generates security events
8	XSS Attack – 50 Reflected XSS Payload Requests	<code>python3 ./auto_xss_attack.py</code>	SIEM Wazuh detects a large number of XSS attempts in a short period of time, logging XSS attack events
9	SSH Login Attempt Attack	<code>ssh user@172.16.32.2</code> (masukkan password yang salah)	SIEM Wazuh detects failed login attempts via SSH and logs them as suspicious activity or attacks and sends notifications to Telegram
10	SSH Brute Force Attack	<code>hydra -l user -P passwords.txt 172.16.32.2 ssh</code>	SIEM Wazuh detects a large number of login attempts in a short time, records brute force attack events, and generates security events
11	Command Injection Attack – Shellshock	<code>curl -H "User-Agent: () { :; }; echo '93e4r0-CVE-2014-6271:"</code>	SIEM Wazuh detects Shellshock commands sent via the User-Agent header

		<code>true';" http://172.16.32 .2/DVWA/</code>	and logs them as command injection attempts. Alerts related to this attack were generated by Wazuh and sent notifications to Telegram
12	Long URL Request Attack	<code>curl "http://172.16.32.2/DVWA/\$(python3 -c 'print("A"* 8000)')"</code>	SIEM Wazuh detects requests with URLs that are too long as an exploitation attempt, and generates events according to the related rules
13	Local File Inclusion (LFI) Attack	<code>http://172.16.32.2/DVWA/vulnerabilities/fi/?page=../../../../../../../../etc/passwd</code>	Attempts to access sensitive files such as /etc/passwd are recorded in Wazuh's SIEM as Local File Inclusion attempts and generate security events
14	File Upload Shell Attack	<code>Upload shell.php dan akses http://172.16.32.2/DVWA/hackable/uploads/shell.php?cmd=whoami</code>	SIEM Wazuh detects the presence of PHP shell files as a potential attack and generates a security event

Table 2 presents tests involving various attacks on the web server to evaluate whether Wazuh can generate alerts for these activities based on the web server logs.